

Social

LEADERSHIP QUALITIES AMONG THE B.ED. STUDENT TEACHERS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract

Education is to improve humanity. Man becomes wise man through education. Education is a powerful instrument of social, economic and cultural transformation necessary for the realization of national goals. Leadership quality is considered as quality an integral part of the teacher education. Leader is one who makes his subordinate to do willingly what he wants. The efforts of subordinates are to be canalized in the right direction. As leaders, they are not only responsible for directing their subordinates but also responsible for the attainment of goals of education. One of the major objective of this study is to investigate Leadership Qualities among B.Ed., Student Teachers based on Gender, Religion, Types of Family, Medium of Study and Educational Qualification of Parents. The Sample 300 B.Ed., Student teachers from 10 colleges in Coimbatore District.

Keywords: Leadership Qualities; Student Teachers; Investigate; Colleges.

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1. Introduction

The word ‘leadership’ has a wide assortment of meanings or interpretations or definitions. More often today than in the past, we find leader being thought of as resource person. Many of research workers and experts have studied about this term from their different views and some of them used it as an administrative, executive, evaluative, sense, qualities of an individual or supervisory behavior and some other used it in a mere limited sense. It is a form of social interaction or process of mutual stimulation between an individual and the members of his/her group. Leadership can be more properly referred to as a ‘leader-follower’ role. Here, the group may be an educational institution, or it may be other types of institution. So, leadership is the ability to influence a group towards the achievement of common goals or it is the process of influencing and supporting others to work enthusiastically towards achieving objectives. Particularly within the field of educational administration, the term ‘leadership qualities’ is a process or act of influencing the movements of

an organized group in its efforts towards goal achievement. In this sense, leadership behavior refers to a relationship between persons or to the interplay among persons.

2. Objectives of the Study

Objectives are the main areas where the investigator will be conducting the study work. There are two main objectives conducting undertaken by the investigator in this study.

2.1. General Objective

To find out the significant score difference in the Leadership qualities among B.ED., student teachers.

2.2. Specific Objectives

To find out the significant score difference in the Leadership qualities among B.ED., student teachers based on

- Gender
- Religion
- Types of Family
- Medium of Study
- Educational Qualification Of Parents

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant mean score difference in B.Ed., student teachers leadership qualities with regard to Gender.

Table 1: Leadership Qualities with regard to Gender

S.No.	Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Table Value	t-value	Remarks
1	Boys	80	1.97	0.14	1.980	0.11	NS
2	Girls	220	1.90	0.20			

Interpretation

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value 0.11 are less than the table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant mean score difference in B.Ed., student teachers leadership qualities with regard to Type of Family.

Table 2: Leadership Qualities with regard to Type of Family

S.No.	Type of Family	N	Mean	S.D.	Table Value	t-value	Remarks
1	Nuclear	197	1.93	0.16	1.980	0.07	NS
2	Joint	103	1.91	0.19			

Interpretation

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value 0.07 are less than the table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant mean score difference in B.Ed., student teachers leadership qualities with regard to Medium of Study.

Table 3: Leadership Qualities with regard to Medium of Study

S.No.	Medium of Study	N	Mean	S.D.	Table Value	t-value	Remarks
1	Tamil	180	1.90	0.18	1.980	0.09	NS
2	English	120	1.93	0.15			

Interpretation

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated t-value 0.09 are less than the table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

3. Conclusion

- The calculated t-value 0.11 are less than the table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant mean score difference in B.Ed., Student Teachers leadership qualities with regard to Gender.
- The calculated t-value 0.07 are less than the table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant mean score difference in B.Ed., Student Teachers leadership qualities with regard to Types of Family.
- The calculated t-value 0.09 are less than the table value 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant mean score difference in B.Ed., Student Teachers leadership qualities with regard to Medium of Study.

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